

EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGIES THAT DEVELOP THE READINESS OF FUTURE TECHNOLOGY TEACHERS FOR INNOVATIVE PROFESSIONAL ACTIVITY

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada Bu turdagi metodlar interfaol ta'limning muhim tarkibiy elementi hisoblanadi. Tizimlashtirishdan ko'zlangan asosiy maqsad ichki ilmiy aloqadorlikni tartibga keltirish yo'li bilan yaxlitlikni yuzaga keltirishdan iboratdir.

Kalit so'zlar va tushunchalar: , o'qituvchi, dars, texnologiya, pedagogika, innovatsiya, faoliyat, rivojlanish, hamkorlik, samaradorlik.

Аннотация: В данной статье данный вид методов является важным компонентом и элементом интерактивного обучения. Основная цель систематизации - внести единство и порядок во внутреннюю науку и общение.

Ключевые слова и понятия: учитель, урок, технология, педагогика, инновации, деятельность, развитие, сотрудничество, эффективность.

Abstract: In this article, this type of methods is an important component and element of interactive education. The main goal of systematization is to bring unity and order to internal science and communication.

Key words and concepts: teacher, lesson, technology, pedagogy, innovation, activity, development, cooperation, efficiency.

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Innovative methods used in the educational process. Innovative methods are also used in the educational system in modern conditions. Among them, the most popular methods are the interactive methods known by the same name.

Interfaol metodlar – talabalarning bilim, ko'nikma, malaka va muayyan axloqiy sifatlarni o'zlashtirish yo'lidagi o'zaro harakatini hamda o'qituvchi bilan hamkorliklarini tashkil etishga xizmat qiladigan metodlar

In this article, this type of methods is an important component and element of interactive education. Currently, there are more than 100 types of interactive methods, and each of them can be used effectively in the educational process, depending on the nature of the educational material and the psychological and psychological characteristics of the students. There is an opportunity to use interactive methods appropriately and effectively within the module "Innovative educational technologies and editorial competence", which is intended to be taught in the training course of HEI editors. Since part 2 of this MOU directly talks about interactive methods that can be effectively used in the teaching process of the module, their content is not discussed in detail here.

Recently, the "Keus-stadi" method has been successfully used in the practice of education in foreign countries, and today it is becoming more and more popular in the education of the

Republic. For this reason, we will talk about the essence of this method (technology)¹ in this place

The main goal of systematization is to bring unity and order to internal science and communication. The quality created in this process will have its own quality indicators.

The essence of integration is to achieve the results of knowledge at the same level as a means of theory and synthesis. The implementation of integrative integration in the educational process can be carried out knowing the internal and external relations of the system or existing form of the integrated object, as well as the laws of its organization and management. Integrative fraternization is used to integrate educational subjects that are related in content, related, logically and mutually demanding, deepening and broadening each other, and envisages the integration of logical and perfect knowledge, methods of work and personal qualities.

The main part: "Technology and design", "Service service" and "Technological education practicum" are the main sections of using modern (innovative, pedagogical and informational) technologies in technology classes. You will learn one of them completely. "Innovation" is education: a process that develops according to certain stages.

Preparing future technology teachers for innovative activities during their education. This activity will be effective and appropriate only if it is carried out as a whole with the work of preparing them for pedagogic activity. . . methods, technologies [8].

The application of innovation in education makes it possible for pedagogues to adapt to changing conditions and use non-standard methods during lessons. Today's modernized education requires new views and approaches from every pedagogue, not limited to old and tested methods. In order to impart knowledge to the students and educate the growing young generation, the pedagogue should be able to involve them in the educational process while embodying creativity, and also achieve effective results. In this, innovative education and approaches help to make the lesson process interesting and serve to develop the content of education [5].

This article is created on the basis of the work carried out in the educational process in the field of Technology in the orientation of students to innovative educational activities in the higher education system. It contains information about the practical-theoretical basis of preparing future technology teachers for innovative activities. Accordingly, instructions were given on how to organize innovative activities for future technology teachers. I think that through this article, practical and theoretical information is enough for future teachers of technology to learn ways to be ready for innovative activities.

The main goal of teaching technology in general secondary educational institutions is to apply the knowledge, skills and competences acquired in the course of technical-technological and technological process operations in independent practical activities, in choosing a profession, national and is to form the competencies to engage in social relations based on universal human values.

¹ Innovatsion ta'lim texnologiyalari / Muslimov N.A., Usmonboeva M.H., Sayfurov D.M., To'raev A.B. – T.: "Sano standart" nashriyoti, 2015. – 81-b.; Сборник кейсов для вузов по дисциплинам гуманитарного и социально-экономического цикла / Учеб.-мет.пособие. – СПб.: Изд-о Санкт-Петербургского университета управления и экономики, 2015. – С. 3.

This, in turn, is the main task of teaching technology not only in higher educational institutions, but also in general secondary educational institutions: studying materials and their properties, characteristics, and information about technical objects and technological processes; knowledge of special and general labor operations in technical objects and technological processes; ability to manage technological processes, apply special and general labor operations in practice; form technical and creative thinking, intellectual abilities; to be able to analyze the technological process and the sequence of execution of prepared products and the quality of products; to draw conclusions about the performance of products and processes and to be able to evaluate labor operations and product quality; to form and develop competences related to basic and technological science in the implementation of conscious preparation for choosing a profession

Ensuring the development and prospects of the Republic of Uzbekistan depends on the changes taking place in the economic, social, political and cultural spheres. In order to actively participate in such changes, high-level general and special knowledge, intellectual it is required to have potential, a broad outlook and skillful use of information communications. Based on these requirements, the training of pedagogic personnel is one of the most important tasks of today [1].

As the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan noted: "Our great goals set before us today, the achievement of our noble intentions, the renewal of our society, the progress and prospects of our lives, the reforms we are implementing, the results of our plans, the fate of all these, above all, meet the requirements of the time, we all understand that it is closely related to the problem of training highly qualified, conscious specialists" [2].

Preparing future technology teachers for innovative activities during their education. This activity will be effective and appropriate only if it is carried out as a whole with the work of preparing them for pedagogical activity.

Innovation (English innovation) is innovation.

M.M. Potashnik's interpretations of innovation processes attract people's attention. It provides the following structure of the innovation process:

the structure of activity - motive - goal - task - content - form - methods are a set of methodological components;

- subjective structure - international, regional, lumen, city and other levels of innovative activity subjects;
- international, regional, district, city and other levels of level structure-innovative activity subjects;
- content structure - emergence, development and assimilation of innovation in educational work, management (etc.);
- life cycle structure based on stages — emergence of innovation — scientific growth — maturity — assimilation — diffusion (absorption, spread) — enrichment (exhaustion) — backwardness — crisis. - irradiation (deception) - modernization;
- management structure - interaction of 4 types of management actions: planning - organizing - leading - controlling;
- organizational structure - diagnostic, predictive, purely organizational, practical, generalizing, implementing.

The innovation process consists of a system that includes structural structures and laws.

Literature review:

The current educational development brought a new direction - innovative pedagogy to the field. The term "innovative pedagogy" and researches specific to it appeared in Western Europe and the USA in the 60s of the 20th century. Innovative activity was studied in the works of F. N. Gonobolin, S. M. Godnin, V. I. Zagyazinsky, V. A. Kan-Kalik, N. V. Kuzmina, V. A. Slastenin, A. I. Shcherbakov. In these studies, innovative activity is covered from the point of view of innovation and wide dissemination of advanced pedagogical experiences [8].

H. Barnet, D. Basset, D. Hamilton, N. Gross, R. Carlson, M. Mayes, A. Haylock, D. Chen, R. Edem. The issues of conditions necessary for "life and activity" were analyzed [9].

Innovative activity of higher education teacher is one of the main problems of higher education pedagogy [8].

Innovation (English innovation) is innovation.

A. I. Prigozhin understands the term innovation as purposeful changes that introduce new, relatively stable elements into a certain social unit, organization, population, society, group. This is the activity of the innovator [7].

Researchers (A. I. Prigozhin, B. V. Sazonov, V. S. Tolstoy, A. G. Kruglikov, A. S. Axiezer, N. P. Stepanov and others) distinguish two approaches to studying the components of innovation processes: the individual microlevel of innovation and the microlevel of the interaction of individually introduced innovations [7].

In the first approach, some new idea brought to life is illuminated.

In the second approach, the interaction of individually introduced innovations. Their unity is their competition and the consequent replacement of one by the other.

This concept stems from the fact that innovation is a measurable process [7].

In the literature on pedagogy, a scheme of the innovation process is given. It covers the following steps:

1. The stage of the birth of a new idea or the emergence of a new concept. It is also called the discovery phase.
2. Inventing, that is, the stage of creating something new.
3. The stage of being able to apply the created innovation in practice.
4. The stage of spreading the news, its wide implementation.
5. The stage of dominance of innovation in a certain field. At this stage, the novelty loses its novelty, its effective alternative appears.
6. On the basis of a new alternative, the stage of reducing the scope of the innovation through replacement.
7. V. A. Slastenin considers innovation as a set of purpose-oriented innovation creation, wide spread and use process, its purpose is to satisfy human needs and aspirations with new means [6].

The authors of the systematic concept of innovation (A. I. Prigozhin, B. V. Sazonov, V. S. Tolstoy) distinguish two important forms of innovation processes.

In the first form, the simple processes of innovation are included. This applies to organizations that are adopting the product for the first time.

The second form refers to the large-scale development of the innovation [7].

Both innovation and internal logic are a dynamic system that develops legally over time and expresses its interaction with the environment.

The concept of "new" occupies a central place in pedagogical innovation. Also, in the science of pedagogy, there is an interest in specific, conditional, internal and subjective innovation.

According to V. A. Slastenin, the private innovation, in the current modernization, involves updating one of the elements of a specific system product [9].

Conditional innovation is a combination of certain elements that lead to complex and progressive innovation. Local novelty is determined by the use of novelty in a specific object. Subjective novelty is determined by the fact that the object itself is new for a given object. The concepts of novelty and innovation are different in scientific areas. Innovation is a tool: a new method, methodology, technology, etc.

"Innovation" is education: a process that develops according to certain stages.

V. I. Zagvyazinsky defined the concept of "new" and said that "new" in pedagogy is not only this idea, but approaches that have not yet been used. methods, technologies [8].

The innovative activity of the teacher is an indispensable part of the educational process. The application of innovation in education makes it possible for pedagogues to adapt to changing conditions and use non-standard methods during lessons. Today's modernized education requires new views and approaches from every pedagogue, not limited to old and tested methods. In order to impart knowledge to the students and educate the growing young generation, the pedagogue should be able to involve them in the educational process and achieve effective results. At the same time, innovative methods and approaches help to make the lesson process interesting and are also promising for the development of educational content [5].

Summary

In this article, it is created on the basis of the work to be done in the educational process in the field of Technology in the orientation of students to innovative pedagogical activities in the higher education system. It contains information about the theoretical basis of preparing future technology teachers for innovative activities. Accordingly, instructions were given on how to organize innovative activities for future technology teachers. Through this article, I think that the theoretical information is enough for future teachers of technology to learn ways to be ready for innovative activities.

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